

Financial Toxicity and Cancer Treatment – A study on Cancer Patients of AMALA Hospital Kerala

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Abstract

Financial toxicity in healthcare is related to the out of pocket expenses made by the patients, which can cause huge financial crisis for them and their families. People face enormous issues in dealing with healthcare costs, especially when they have to tackle with poor health condition due to terminal illness like Cancer. Affordable cancer care and control has become an important matter of concern. Kerala, with high rate of literacy and health consciousness among people, has a well-established system for cancer care in the public sector as well as private sector, even though access to treatment, early diagnosis and management of cancer is a hurdle to the state. The aim of this research is to understand the financial problems faced by cancer patients at AIMS Kerala. The study showed the importance of introducing cost effective methods in Cancer care and suggested PPP in overall cancer care facilities as one of the solution for reducing financial toxicity.

Introduction

The terms financial toxicity or financial distress in healthcare are related to the out of pocket expenses made by the patients, which can cause huge financial crisis for them and their families. Out-of-pocket expenses are those costs that you pay for your medical care which are not covered by your health insurance. People face enormous issues in dealing with healthcare costs, especially when they have to tackle with poor health condition due to terminal illness like Cancer. Huge medical expenditure for treatment leads to physical, mental, emotional distress and most importantly financial toxicity to the patient and their family.

Cancer, which is also known as malignancy, is basically an abnormal growth of cells which are infected. There are more than 100 types of cancer. Symptoms, problems and treatment vary depending on the type of cancer. Cancer treatment may include mainly chemotherapy, radiation, and surgery.

Analysis published by The Lancet Oncology showed Kerala has the highest number of cancer patients followed by Mizoram, Haryana, Delhi and Karnataka, but the death rate for both male and female due to cancer is highest in Mizoram followed by Kerala and Haryana.

**Table 1 Crude Cancer Incidences
(Per 100000 Populations)**

States	1990	2016
Kerala	74.1	135.3
Mizoram	89.1	121.7
Haryana	71	103.3
Delhi	64.6	102.9
Karnataka	76.2	101.6

Source: The Lancet Oncology

The development of research on cancer treatments is considered as an important focus pharmaceutical research. This improved treatment and care in past decade, which comes at a considerable expense, and difficult for the patients to bear.

Above that, not having regular and consistent income, losing job, reduced income due to illness is psychologically and financially depressing. Along with rigid treatment plans, regular medicines and healthy diet add on to the financial woes.

Cancer Care Centre’s in India

Affordable cancer care and control has become an important matter of concern to all developing economies, especially India where cancer incidence are increasing rapidly. This rapid growth in cancer incidence in the country increased the demand for cancer care options. Several non-governmental, non-profit, national institutes for awareness, detection, and providing cure and treatment for cancer patients in India were started. Some of them are as follows:

- Indian Cancer society
- Sri Ratan TATA trust
- Tata Memorial Hospital, Mumbai
- Kidwai Memorial Institute of Oncology, Bangalore
- Tata Memorial Hospital, Kolkata
- Regional Cancer Center, Thiruvananthapuram
- Cancer Care Foundation of India, Mumbai

Crucial issues of infrastructure, shortage of qualified manpower, and the need to develop practical solutions for prevention and early detection of cancer has become a matter of immediate concern. Managing the large unregulated private sector and the cost of new technologies and drugs also need to be addressed by the government. In this scenario, the role of public insurance schemes, Public Private Participatory Projects, new political agendas and setting priorities, the much needed improvement in the quality of care, and importance of cost effective care program plays an important role.

Cancer Patients Welfare Scheme by Government of Kerala

Government of Kerala introduced number of schemes to help to reduce the financial toxicity of the cancer patients. Major schemes are as follows

Scheme	Eligibility	Age	Benefit	Available
Cancer Suraksha Scheme	APL and BPL	Up to 18	Free treatment	Govt. hospitals and RCC
Karunya Benevolent Fund	Annual income less than 3,00,000	Any Age	Up to 2,00,000/-	Govt. hospitals, RCC and KBF registered private hospitals
Sukrutham	BPL	Any Age	Up to 3,00,000/-	Govt. hospitals and RCC
Financial aid from society for the poor	Low socio economic background	Any age	Up to 50,000/-	Govt. hospitals and RCC
RashtriyaArogya Nidhi	Low income Group			
Chemotherapy, surgery, radiation and scans	Any age	Up to 2,00,000/-	Mainly in Govt. Hospitals and RCC	
Cancer Pension Scheme	Support after treatment for BPL	Any Age	1000/- per month	Lifelong

Source: <http://www.socialsecuritymission.gov.in/schemes.php>

Amala Institute of Medical Science

One of the oldest cancer care centre in Kerala since 1978, Amala institute of medical science has established a research centre namely Amala Cancer Research Centre in 1982. It was established as a nonprofit, charitable Christian management institution specialized for cancer treatment. It was inaugurated by the then President of India NeelamSanjiva Reddy. It was known as Amala Hospital since it developed as a private medical college. They also run Palliative care unit in the campus and support patients who live nearby to the hospital. They have qualified and specialized doctors, well trained nursing care, all modern technology and treatments, social worker department, special counselors, and trained volunteers to give holistic care for cancer patients. This Hospital is the life saver for many cancer patients in Kerala, especially patients from Thrissur, Palaghat and Malapuram Districts.

Review of Literature

JayalekshmiPadmavathyAmma, Paul Sebastian of RCC, Thiruvananthapuram in their study Burden of Cancer, Registry Data Base study of Kerala (2012) examined challenges faced by the public health departments for prevention and control of cancer. They also analysed the ways by which public health departments can improve the quality of life of cancer patients. Emphasis should be given to cancer control activities by taking Cancer as a notifiable disease.

Bhawna Sirohi (2014) in a study Cancer care delivery in India at the grassroot level: Improve outcomes said India is equally good in cancer care services provided compared to western countries. The private care providers in Indian cancer care sector are well equipped with the best technology and qualified doctors. Lack of core guidelines to define a cancer centre, government regulations to regulate pricing, and awareness about cancer is a matter of concern.

Delivery of affordable and equitable cancer care in India by C S Pramesh, Rajendra A Badwe, Bibhuti B Borthakur, Madhu Chandra and others discussed the role of public insurance scheme, priorities to be set by the government, different political outlook and the need of quality health care provision.

National Cancer Institute, USA conducted a study on Risk Factors Related to Financial Toxicity (Financial Distress) among cancer patients in 2018. The study revealed that type of cancer, severity and the treatment received can lead to financial distress. Other factors like age, community, income, job and type of health insurance patients have will also affect financial security.

Getting Cancer Treatment in India by Jasmine Marfatia (2018) raised the concerns because according to her study 18% knowingly delaying medical treatment after being diagnosed, due to financial barriers. This shows failure of insurance, government schemes etc. Researcher suggested cancer Crowdfunding as one of the solution for the issue.

Objectives

1. To analyse the financial problems faced by the patients without health insurance at AIMS
2. To understand the effectiveness of Government insurance schemes among cancer patients of AIMS
3. To suggest cost effective practices of cancer care for the vulnerable populations.

Research Methodology

The type of research used in this study is exploratory research with qualitative and quantitative variables. This research is based on sample survey with convenience sampling method. Sample size is 20 and sampling unit is cancer patients at AIMS. The type of data collection method used in research is primary data collection method with a structured questionnaire. The statistical tools used for the study are averages, percentages

Scope of Study

Scope of this study is limited to financial related problems of cancer patients at AMALA Institute of Medical Science, Thrissur and the need for quality care centers and cost effective economic practices for Cancer Patients.

Analysis

Primary data collected for this research with the structured questionnaires is collected from 20 respondents who are taking treatment from AMALA Institute of Medical Science for Cancer. Among them 55% are male, 60% fall under the age category of 40-70 and most of them 75% are from the same district Thrissur.

Cancer Type

Majority of female respondents are taking treatment for breast cancer, and male respondents for stomach related cancer

Table 3

Type	Number	Percentage	Gender
Breast	4	20%	F-4
Lungs	2	10%	M-2
Stomach	5	25%	M-4 F-1
Throat	1	5%	M
Ovary	1	5%	F
Kidney	1	5%	F

Liver	1	5%	M
Lymphoma	1	5%	F
Brain	1	5%	M
bone	1	5%	F
Mouth	1	5%	M
Blood	1	5%	M

As majority of the respondents falls under 40-70 category, 25% of them are retired professionals. 75% including retired respondents and house wives are not working. 15% work part time and 10% are on leave for the treatment.

Cost Per Treatment

55% of the total respondents pay 10000 to 15000 per treatment (only treatment like chemotherapy, radiation etc.). 10% pay more than 20000 per treatment. Treatment cost varies from patient to patient depending on the type and stage of cancer. Cost of treatment also changes with the age of the patient.

Insurance Coverage

The important factor in reducing financial toxicity of patients is the insurance coverage. Among the respondents 65% have insurance coverage, but insurance is not covering the entire cost of treatment and process, which increases the financial burden of the patients. It is quiet alarming that 76% among those who insured have Private insurance which shows urgent need for government initiatives to increase the number of people covered with govt. insurance scheme. Action must be taken by the govt. and the private hospital to accept government insurance in the private hospital.

Raising Fund by Patients

Graph - 1

Financial burden of the patients increases as they try to fill the gap by raising fund for treatment through borrowing, loan, selling property and gold. Even upper middle class with savings also suffer as they will be wiped out of savings for their future.

Reasons for Choosing AMALA

55% of the respondents ranked unprofessionalism by the government care centers as the main factor for choosing AMALA. 60% give their second reason for choosing AMALA as the non-

availability of government care centers. Timely treatment and Doctors at AMALA also are reasons for choosing the hospital for treatment, but most of the respondents ranked price of AMALA is very high than government care centers.

Graph – 2 Reasons for Choosing AMALA

Overall Satisfaction Level of AMALA

65% of the respondents are satisfied with the overall performance of AMALA hospital. They are happy with the doctors, infrastructure and timely treatment by the hospital. Having good infrastructure, on time treatment and professional doctors are very important factors for successful Cancer treatment.

Graph – 4

Cost of Treatment Leads to Financial Problems

50% agrees and 50% strongly agrees that cost of the treatment leads to financial problems for them irrespective of their financial position

Financial Problems Leads to Depression

Financial problems due to high expense of treatment may lead to depression among some patients. 55% agreed and 40% strongly agreed that increased financial burden leads to depression. 5% were neutral on the statement.

Graph – 5

Financial Problems Breaks Treatment

In India, due to financial problems people used to break the treatment, but serious ailments like Cancer will get complicated if timely treatment is not given. 45% agreed and 35% strongly agreed that financial problems can break the treatment.

All the respondents, irrespective of the financial status were recommending the need for Government insurance scheme and innovative policies by the government to reduce financial burden faced by the Cancer patients.

Cost Effective Practices of Cancer Care for the Vulnerable Populations

Increasing cost of healthcare management and high out of pocket expenditure by the people for funding their medical treatment, demands the government and the private players to work on implementing cost effective practices in medical treatment. The research derives the importance of need for government insurance and strict policies to accept the same by all hospitals.

Major Solutions for Reducing Financial Burden for Cancer Patients

- Govt. initiatives and policies to reduce financial burden by controlling cost of treatment
- Govt. Insurance Scheme especially for all Cancer patients considering income level of patients.
- Mass awareness and education program as early detection reduces the financial burden and increases the cancer survival rate.
- Public Private Participation programs for treatment, awareness, and all allied services related to Cancer.

Significance of Public-Private Participation in Healthcare and Allied Services

A public-private partnership (PPP) is a government service or private business venture which is funded and operated through a partnership of government and one or more private sector companies. The model looks into a partnership between the public healthcare facilities and the private ones. The model has successfully worked in various other sectors like roads, airports, telecom, irrigation, education etc.

Findings

- Lack of Cancer awareness and education program is one of the reasons for increasing incidence of Cancer in the country
- Cancers can be prevented, screened for and/or detected early and treated at an early stage

- Huge medical expenditure leads to financial toxicity to the patient and their family. It also leads to Physical, mental, emotional distress.
- Irregular income, Losing job, Reducing income due to illness, rigid treatment plans, Regular medicines and Healthy diet Add to the financial woes of the patient and family.
- There is increase in the rate of cancer survival worldwide with growth of cancer research, but it also increased Price of treatment.
- Both Government and Private insurance fail to cover the complete expenditure of cancer treatment, and majority of them have private insurance.
- Unprofessionalism by govt. centers and non-availability for public care centers is the major reason for avoiding Government care centers.

Suggestions

- Proper PPP initiatives will work wonders in providing quality and economical healthcare to vulnerable population.
- PPP also should be extended to allied services including awareness and educating people about Cancer and other serious ailments.
- Increase the financial assistance of KarunyaBenevolent Fund for eligible patients and Separate AyushmanBharath funding for Cancer patients.
- Provide affordable accommodation facilities near government centers.

Conclusion

The healthcare sector in India is undergoing a phase of reform propelled by economic growth of the country. Apart from the healthcare providers, emerging markets such as diagnostic chains and medical device manufacturers, social and other allied services also should contribute to PPP projects. Government is trying to focus on providing health security provision to each and every individual with a highly innovative, affordable, and accessible health system. For a successful health care, the bureaucracy should be proactive. With the modification in certain administrative systems and procedures we can attain world class health provision. Government has to focus on good health and wellbeing for the citizens throughout their lives and should try to reduce the time lag in dispersing the fund to the people.

References

1. Jayalekshmi Padmavathy Amma, Paul Sebastian RCC, Thiruvananthapuram(2012)Burden of Cancer, Registry Data Base study of Kerala, Journal of Health Systems (JHS) Vol 2 No 1 (2017): January to June, 2017.
2. Bhawna Sirohi (2014) Cancer care delivery in India at the grass root level: Improve outcomes Indian Journal of medical and pediatric oncology Volume 35, issue 3 page 187-191.
3. Jeffrey D Miller, Kathleen A Foley Mason W Russell (2014) Current Challenges in Health Economic Modeling of Cancer Therapies, Journal American health and drug benefits, Volume 7(3) Page 153-162.
4. Laura AV Marlow and Jane Wardle (2014) Scale to assess cancer stigma among the non-patient population BMC Cancer 201414:285 <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2407-14-285>
5. Dr. A Venkat Raman and Dr James Warner 2006 “Public-Private Partnership in the Provision of Health Services for the Poor” funded by the Indo-Dutch Programme on Alternatives in Development (IDPAD) Chapter V Pg.No: 1-50.

6. Ghosh, S. 2011. Catastrophic Payments and Impoverishment due to Out-of-Pocket Health Spending. Economic and Political Weekly. Vol - XLVI No. 47, November 19.
7. Good Health at Low Cost. (1985) Proceedings of the Bellagio Conference, Bellagio, Italy, The Rockefeller Foundation, World Health forum Vol. 7 Pg.No: 433-438
8. Indrani Gupta, (2009) Institute of Economic Growth, Delhi, "Out of pocket Expenditure and Poverty, Estimates from NSS 61st Round. Pg.No:1-19
9. K.P. Kannan, K.R. Thankappan, V. Ramankutty and K. P. Aravindan,(1991) Health and Development in Rural Kerala. Kerala Sastra Sahitya Parishad, Trivandrum, Pg. No: 1-50.
10. M. Govinda Rao and Mita Choudhury (2012) National Institute of Public Finance and Policy "Health Care Financing Reforms in India" Pg.No:1-24
11. P.G.K. Panikar and C.R. Soman, (1985) Health Status of Kerala: The Paradox of Economic Backwardness and Health Development. Centre for Development Studies, Trivandrum, Pg. No: 120-156
12. Sarosh Kuruvilla, Mingwei Liu, Priti Jacob (2005) "The Karnataka Yeshaswini Health Insurance Scheme For Rural Farmers & Peasants: Towards Comprehensive Health Insurance Coverage For Karnataka?" Paper Prepared for the Social Science and Development Conference in Karnataka Pg.No: 1-45.
13. UCL School of Pharmacy (2013) "Health and Healthcare in India" Pg.No 1-36
14. Jasmine Marfatia (2018) Getting Cancer Treatment in India
15. Next Billion Health care "All about India-A Healthcare Market in Transition" <http://healthmarketinnovations.org/blog/all-about-india-health-care-market-transition> Viewed on 26/02/2014
16. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Union Budget 2017-18
17. NitiAayog health index
18. District Level Household and Facility Survey (2015-16)
19. Regional Cancer Centre, Trivandrum Annual report
20. Amala Institute of medical science website
21. <http://cancerindia.org.in/cancer-statistics>